

OPEN SCIENCE AND PSYCHOPHYSICS: TOOLS TO STUDY THE MIND

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Abstract

Background: psychophysics and quantitative methods

There is a long honourable history of using quantitative data to study the human mind. It comprises numerical measures of performance that vary among individuals and may be affected by experience, training and motivation; and laws relating these measures to each other. Raw measures include: sensation via magnitude estimation and Likert categories; discrimination as proportions of hits and false alarms; and reaction time. Derived theoretical measures include: Steven's power law coefficient; d' and associated response bias criteria; information accrual rate for timed tasks with associated speed accuracy criteria. Much of experimental psychology uses statistics to estimate these descriptive measures and their variance; to test hypotheses about whether predictor effects according to task or population might have occurred by chance (p-value); and the magnitude of any predictor relative to the inherent variability of the target measures (effect size).

The replicability crisis and the Open Science movement

Recently many hallowed experimental results have been called into question as replications fail or are impossible due to unavailability of raw data or details of statistical methods. There is also systematic bias, as non-significant results may not be reported.

Criteria for effective Open Science tools in response to the crisis are considered, including good graphics, effect sizes, and non-linear options. I have created a set of infographic tools embodying Open Science guidelines. These comprise: overview; abstract; introduction (purpose and prior knowledge); sample description (method 1); variables (method 2); analyses including code (method 3); graphic summaries (results 1); descriptive statistics (results 2); inferential statistics (results3); summary and impact; references; acknowledgements; supplementary material; pre-registration. Example use free R based package JAMOVI. G^* is useful for a priori power and Lenhard's package for interpreting effect sizes. R, which may require coding, is recommended for more complex theoretical parameter estimation, e.g., for information accrual models.

AI and large language tools are available for: literature reviews, automated summaries of documents and across articles, data extraction and chat functions (Consensus, Scitex, Elicit, SciSpace). AI writing assistants may help with paraphrasing/summarising (Quillbot, Jenni). Map based systems provide cross literature links (Litmaps, Researchrabbit, Connectedpapers). How these evolving tools fare for psychophysics is explored, with some interesting and amusing results.

Summary

Open Science tools are a natural, if arduous, evolution from early psychophysics. In my view they are the way forward to enhance progress in scientific psychology and psychophysics.

Open science and psychophysics: quantitative tools to study the mind

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Plan

➤ Review history of psychophysics

- ❑ Early attempt to quantify psychological phenomena
Psychophysics, Quantitative Psychology
- ❑ Sensation, performance, reaction time, errors
- ❑ Models: signal detection, Information accrual, Decisions

➤ Open Science

- ❑ Movement
- ❑ Tools

➤ Artificial intelligence

- ❑ Information communication: learning, teaching, advocacy
- ❑ Literature review tools: references, grey literature
- ❑ Data analysis
- ❑ Useful prompts and strategies

Open Science: Movement and Practice

➤ Replicability Crisis

- ❑ Many treasure psychological and medical studies do not replicate

Poor design: recruitment [too few, WEIRD], methods and materials not specified

Community discourages replication > file draw problem

➤ Response

- ❑ Guidelines: Mss., Journals, Reviewers

- ❑ Registered reports

➤ Guidelines

- ❑ Minimal not advocacy

- ❑ Includes further resources

- ❑ Can be used as check list

- ❑ Version 1: single page infographic

- ❑ Version 2a: infographic for each stage

- ❑ Version 2b: results examples using JAMOVI [R-based, free, click and drop interface]

Open Transparent Replicable Science Guide

❖ Investigation Stages from Start to Finish

❖ [Open Internet Principles](#)

❖ [Open Science Principles](#)

- [FAIR](#) **F**indable, **A**ccessible, **I**nteroperable, **R**eusable
- [Open Science Foundation](#) [UK Reproducibility Network](#)

❖ Section [1](#). Planning and Record Keeping

❖ Section [2](#). Report or Ms. Production

- Include **Data Statement with** doi for deposit, email for data/materials authoriser

❖ Section [3](#). Permanent Supplement, if too long for main Ms/appendix

- Material (stimuli, protocols...); Analysis; Code; Raw Data (numeric, qualitative); tables, figures
- Useful depositories: Author Institution or Public, e.g. Figshare OSF
NOT journal/publisher site if behind paywall, as not **Accessible**

1. Planning, Recording, Execution

- ❑ **Keep good records of progress**
 - ❑ As plans evolve and decision are made
 - ❑ Essential to good science
 - ❑ Data management plan *from start* [OSF](#), [ESRC](#)
 - ❑ Ensure **secure** backup
 - ❑ Consider [project management](#) tools in R
- ❑ **File/folder [names](#)**: Memorable, searchable, sortable
 - ❑ Start with date as YYYYMMDD (either start or last modified)
 - ❑ Author (if not **confidential**). Topic/Project; possibly subtopic
- ❑ **Folder for each project**: Possibly sub-folders for each study
 - ❑ **Confidential** material held separately
 - ❑ All replicability information: materials, procedures, analyses
 - ❑ Project data: all versions
 - ❑ Draft Mss, blogs, announcements, summaries, etc.

1.1 Global Resources for many projects

❖ Frequently used templates

- Journals
- Ethics forms
- [Lab notebooks](#), Lab reports, etc.

❖ Reference database for ALL projects

- Zotero, Mendelev, Endnote (expensive but can migrate) etc.
- One database for all projects
- Topic and Ms, specific sub-folders

❖ Calendar: key dates including deadlines

❖ Contacts: colleagues, journal or sponsors, etc.

1.1 Replicability Plans Folder

❖ Memorable name + start & current date YYYY/MM/DD format, easy sort

- *Always record, as decisions are made*
- Copy/paste between items. EFFICIENT
- Option 1: Record in completely free form logbook file
- Option 2: Record direct into component Ms. files or tools
- Data management, Pre-registration, Ethics, Ms. Supplement

❖ Documents [one or more] for:

- Goals for introduction, informs analysis
- Method: Instruments, tools, variables, analyses
- Results implications and conclusions
- Data management plan, UKRC, EU
- Other communication files: blog, summaries, conferences
- Conferences, press releases, blog, social media, include doi of main report

1.2 Data folder **Some confidential**

❖ Keep & backup initial and final versions, **ALL** files, versions

❖ 1.2.1 Completely Raw Data. **Confidential**

- As collected. May be in special format of package
- Video, audio, text: qualitative data. Productions: drama, art, media
- Pictures for brain scans, location data

❖ 1.2.2 Universally readable numeric Raw Data

Text or spreadsheet. As exported from package: may include **Confidential**

❖ 1.2.3 Tidy: text/csv or spreadsheet. **Confidential**

- Unneeded columns removed, interpretable column names
- Upload to secure site, e.g. institution one drive

❖ 1.2.4 Shareable data for Supplement Anonymised

- ALL shareable data. **Highly desirable**
- Data supporting results/conclusions. **Essential**
 - Include all *individual* parameter estimates supporting summary Tables or Grab[h
- Numeric data: text or spreadsheet, headed columns

2 Full Report or Ms

- **2.0 Abstract, Highlights**
- **2.1 Introduction** Aims, Previous Knowledge, Predictions
- **2.2 Methods** Preliminary, data collection, analysis
- **2.3 Results**
- **2.4 Discussion & Conclusion**
- **2.5 Data practices statement** [EU](#), [ESRC](#)
- **2.6 References, Appendices** (if any)
- **2.7 Other** Author, affiliation, acknowledgments, etc

2.1 Methods: Preparation

- **Pre-registration**
 - ❑ UK Reproducibility Network [Pre-reg Primer](#)
 - ❑ Includes key methods information. Status yes/no
- **Ethics: awarding body, protocols**
 - ❑ Confidentiality openness conflicts
 - ❑ Ethics of investigating unchangeable biodata e.g. sex, ethnicity,
BUT NOT environmental covariates such as deprivation, education level
Insufficient data to draw conclusions: consider power
- **Tools & methods**
 - Survey packages; experiment generators, trackers, etc.
 - Psychological instruments e.g. 'big 5', depression, IQ, etc.
- **Materials, protocols, procedures: sufficient data to be replicable**
- **Data type(s)/variables: quantitative, qualitative, audio visual, other**
- **Selection of units**
 - Participants, studies for meta-analysis, other
 - Recruitment, acquisition, sampling, selection criteria

2.2 Methods: Data Collection

❖ Raw variables and roles

- Not analysed. Needed for sampling and generalisability
 - E.g. bio data: age, sex ethnicity, etc. **Keep separate** if confidential

❖ Quantitative analysis

- Variable roles: E.g. response, predictor, moderator, etc.
- Numeric cleaning procedures E.g. outlier removal
- Numeric summarising procedures E.g.
 - Totalling test scores, categorising total test scores
 - Proportion, mean, other parameter from repeated trials

❖ Qualitative acquisition. E.g. text, audio, video, etc.

❖ Other e.g. scans, trackers, artistic products, etc.

❖ Anonymising procedures, GDPR

- Remove names, locations.
- Remove identifying variable combinations

2.3 Methods: Analyses

➤ Quantitative

- Specify all variables and roles (e.g. response, predictor, mediator, moderator)
- Specify **descriptive** summary parameters
 - E.g. mean, proportion, range, variance, skew, percentiles
- Specify **inferential** tests, e.g. F, t, chi-square, Bayes
- Models specify structure, parameters, fit indices
- Specify a priori & exploratory hypotheses
 - Specify **effect size**: relative to SD or variance accounted for
 - **Frequentist**: power and p-null (confidence) criterion
 - **Bayesian**: priors, a priori probability
- Analysis package and/or software
 - JAMOVI, JASP free, easy to use, excellent graphics, includes Bayes
 - E.g. SPSS v28.1 GENERALIZED LINEAR MODELS
- Code or script: supplement if complex else in Ms. (main or annexe)

➤ Qualitative: specify summary methods e.g. tools

➤ Other summary methods, e.g. scans **composite** composite or individual

➤ Current recommendation is in Methods section, earlier often in results

2.4 Results: at least one of ...

❖ Descriptive statistics: text, tables, graphic figures

- Whole sample: histograms, hazard functions, quantile plots, violin plots.
- Summary: means, range, percentage, box plots, diagrams

❖ Frequentist inferential statistics

- Inferential statistic (t, F, chi-square, etc with degrees of freedom
- Standard errors, confidence limits, effect size, p-null

❖ Bayes inferential statistics

- Priors, Credibility Limits
- Probability null and alternative hypothesis(es), Bayes Factors
- Guides to [using Bayes](#) in free software JASP

❖ Quantitative Models

- Description: parameters, structure
- Criteria for model comparisons, goodness of fit: AIC, BIC, WIC, etc.

❖ Qualitative summary

- Themes, categories, examples, etc.

❖ Other, e.g. visual scans, arts products

3.1 Replicatory Supplement: Where?

📄 Institutional repository: e.g. [University of Hertfordshire](#)

📄 Public: e.g. [OSF](#), [Figshare](#)

📄 As part of Ms. submission

📄 Do not use journal unless Open Access, state location of data

📄 Issues

📄 Where is deposit of *record*?

❑ Some automatic linkage

📄 How are restrictions implemented?

📄 Regulations on ownership etc.

3.2 Replicability Supplement: What?

- ❑ Materials, protocols, ethics: if too complex for main Ms. or Appendices
 - ❑ Formats include: audio, visual, media, surveys, experiment generators etc.
- ❑ **Data:** May be discipline specific. e.g. human is anonymised GDPR, special for [internet studies](#)
 - ❑ Supporting ALL results **required**. All shareable **desirable**, but **NOT required**
 - 📖 Quantitative numeric, Format FAIR = Accessible
 - ❑ ReadMe.txt with variable details; data set(s) comma separated values, CSV
Recommended
 - ❑ Spreadsheet (e.g. EXCEL, googles sheets): ReadMe sheet + sheet for each data set. **Easier to use**
 - ❑ Spreadsheet details in or spreadsheet format ESSENTIAL for FAIR, Accessible
 - ❑ **NEVER** package format e.g. SPSS .SAV, as NOT **Free**.
 - ❑ **NEVER** unstable free software, e.g. R, Python, may not be **Reusable**
 - ❑ Other data: raw scans, transcripts etc.
- 📖 **Analysis Codes and Scripts:** if too complex for main Ms. or Appendices
 - ❑ Free code, e.g. R or Python. Proprietary syntax/code as text, e.g. SPSS, SAS
 - ❑ Software (e.g. C, Stan) code with version & operating system

Artificial Intelligence for Research

➤ ChatGPT 4.0.1 general Large Language Model, LLM

- ❑ <https://chatgpt.com/> Paid version to explore
- ❑ Invents references and other data

➤ Knowledge Summary & Acquisition

- ❑ History, dates, references, key people
- ❑ Idea generation, brainstorming
- ❑ Information: Psychophysics, Signal detection, Reaction time, Information accrual, decisions
- ❑ Literature search

➤ Advocacy, marketing and writing/rewriting

- ❑ International Society for Psychophysics, Radical statistics,
- ❑ Open Science Foundation, Campaign for Science Engineering, Scholars at risk
- ❑ Ms. and conference abstracts
- ❑ Research and innovation proposals

➤ Other AI tools: vision, speech recognition, visual productivity

Artificial intelligence in Academic writing

➤ AI's impact

Khalifa, M., & Albadawy, M. (2024). Using artificial intelligence in academic writing and research: An essential productivity tool. *Computer Methods and Programs in Biomedicine Update*, 5, 100145. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cmpbup.2024.100145>

➤ **Academic writing and research is transforming practices**

- Source 24 studies from major databases since 2019 highlights
- Necessitating broader integration and ethical use in research

➤ **AI enhances academic writing in six areas:**

- idea generation; content structuring; literature synthesis
- data management ; editing; ethical compliance

➤ ChatGPT benefits

- helps manage complex ideas and extensive information
- demonstrates significant potential in academic writing

➤ ChatGPT challenges

- academic integrity
- AI-human balance

➤ **•Future recommendations for ongoing AI research in academia**

- Training, ethical usage, and transparent integration in workflows.

Useful Prompts

➤ Audience

- Academic: student: UG, PG, research, conference promotion, society promotion
- Lay: most important results, market

➤ Format

- Table with specified columns, format suitable for copying
- Reference list with doi, format for reference manager (zotero, mendelev, endnote)
- Save dialogue as word file. Do it OFTEN. Specify ALL words from you and assistant
Searching chatgpt output is a **NIGHTMARE**

➤ Detail

- Start general
- Refine by additions, and breakdown

➤ Type

- Summary, CV, job application

➤ Advice?

Idea generation

URL	Score	Source	Score	Source
jasper.ai	4.7/5	Trustpilot		
chatgpt	2.3/5	chatgpt	4.6/5	OpenAI Community
sudowrite.com	4.5/5	Capterra		
notion.so	4.4/5	G2		
rytr.me	4.4/5	Trustpilot		
inkforall.com	4.3/5	Product Hunt		
wordtune.com	4.2/5	Capterra		
scite.ai	4.2/5	ResearchGate		

Knowledge Acquisition

- **Aim: What might general public learn of our discipline?**
- **Request to chatgpt “History psychophysics & quantitative psychology”**
 - ❑ **Psychophysics detail** **from dialogue or my knowledge**
Models, reaction time, information accrual signal detection, binary decisions
Names **I got 2 imaginary references**
 - ❑ **Quantitative**
Intelligence
- **Measurement in psychology**
 - ❑ **variable type** **no mention Likert**
 - ❑ **analysis** **no mention generalized linear models, effect sizes**
ANOVA, non-parametrics. As old-fashioned text
- **Generally poor**
 - ❑ **Need good secondary reference or text. AI may or may not find**

Knowledge Acquisition Limitations

➤ Key topics omitted

- ❑ DDM direct diffusion model, **not LBA linear ballistic accumulator**

➤ Invented references

- ❑ Also invented DOI, **could not perform check of existence**

➤ Misattribution

- ❑ **Steve Link LBA**

Eventually dissuaded with “exact text for Steve Link and LBA”

Told off chatgpt. Got apology

Next time as chatgpt remembers previous dialogue:

Got LBA names correct. Steve detached from LBA, but still insisted his work was precursor!

➤ Traditional sources better for literature search

- ❑ **But general search helps with search keywords**
- ❑ **Web of Science Scopus, GoogleScholar**

Chatgpt missed

➤ Several early psychophysicists showed an interest in parapsychology, as it was closely related to investigations of human perception and consciousness. A few notable figures include:

1. Gustav Fechner – Known as the father of psychophysics, Fechner also had a strong interest in spiritualism and parapsychology. His work in measuring the relationship between stimuli and sensations extended into his metaphysical beliefs, where he explored concepts of the soul and the afterlife. Sent from my iPhone

Moving ON: some examples

➤ Rewriting

- ❑ Abstracts
- ❑ Book plugs: [Maverick](#) on my WordPress [Amazon](#)
- ❑ Society information

Please rewrite this to attract new members, followed by above text

➤ Attracting students to psychology by country and level

➤ Literature Reviews

ChatGpt abstract this presentation:

Psychophysics, Quantitative Methods, and Open Science

- Psychophysics has a long tradition of using quantitative data to understand the human mind, focusing on measurable variables like sensation, discrimination, and reaction time. Key theoretical measures include Steven's power law coefficient, signal detection theory metrics (d'), and information accrual rates in timed tasks. Statistical methods are widely used to estimate these measures, test hypotheses, and assess the impact of various predictors.
- The replication crisis and the Open Science movement have raised concerns about the reliability of past findings, leading to demands for more transparency and accessibility in research. Effective Open Science tools should include clear visualizations, effect sizes, and non-linear modelling options. Various platforms (e.g., JAMOVI, G*, R) can aid in this process.
- AI and large language tools are becoming increasingly useful in research. Tools like Consensus, Scitex, Elicit, and SciSpace can perform literature reviews, automate document summaries, and extract data. Writing assistants like Quillbot and Jenni help with paraphrasing and summarizing, while map-based systems like Litmaps, Researchrabbit, and Connectedpapers assist in linking research across studies. These tools are still evolving but are showing promising applications in psychophysics.
- Open Science is seen as a challenging but essential progression from the early days of psychophysics, promising to improve the rigor and reproducibility of psychological research.

ChatGpt short: Psychophysics, Quantitative Methods, and Open Science

- Psychophysics employs quantitative data to explore the human mind, using measures like sensation, discrimination, and reaction time. Key theoretical metrics include Steven's power law coefficient and signal detection theory measures (d'). Statistical methods help estimate these metrics and test hypotheses.
- The replication crisis has driven a push for transparency and accessibility, with Open Science tools (e.g., JAMOVI, G*, R) enhancing research practices.
- AI tools, including large language models like ChatGPT, are increasingly used for literature research and knowledge acquisition. Tools like Consensus, Scitex, Elicit, and SciSpace aid in automated summaries and data extraction, while Quillbot helps with paraphrasing and map-based tools link research across studies. These evolving technologies support advancements in psychophysics.
- **This even shorter version is muddled and I would not use**

According to Needs and Abilities, Universal Basic Income Requires Universal Basic Infrastructure

➤ Original

This Ms. considers Universal Basic Income (UBI) as a method for establishing a good society that fulfils the needs of all its members without coercion. It starts with a brief description of UBI and of the good society it aims to create. Various models of basic human needs are considered. Next, we consider non-human and human resources available to create a good society and how they are or might be distributed. This leads to consideration of the types of infrastructure that might be available and how they impact on the level of UBI. An example of how health infrastructure contributes to life expectancy and excess deaths during the covid19 pandemic is included. Some current examples of UBI are discussed together with an evaluation of their efficacy. Measurement is clearly key to evaluation and available and desirable measures are described with special attention to the "Our World in Data" web site. The pros and cons of UBI are discussed. Finally, we conclude that UBI is a useful radical starting point, but that serious progress requires consideration of generations of resources and of allocation of those resources between universal infrastructure and universal individual basic income.

➤ Chat

This paper examines Universal Basic Income (UBI) as a pathway to creating a "good society," one that meets the needs of all members without coercion. Beginning with an overview of UBI and its envisioned societal impact, we explore different frameworks for defining basic human needs. We then assess both human and non-human resources and their distribution in building such a society, focusing on how these influence the potential structure and levels of UBI. The paper also provides a concrete example of how infrastructure, such as healthcare, directly affects outcomes like life expectancy and mortality rates during events like the COVID-19 pandemic. We review real-world UBI trials and critically evaluate their outcomes, emphasizing the role of measurement in assessing their impact. A detailed discussion of measurement tools, with a focus leading to a broader discussion on resource generation and allocation. The conclusion posits UBI as a valuable radical step toward equity but underscores the need to balance universal infrastructure with individual basic income for sustainable progress on the "Our World in Data" website, is included to illustrate how to track and evaluate UBI's efficacy. Pros and cons of UBI are presented,

International Society for Psychophysics. Chatgpt 2

➤ Why Join Us?

➤ Annual Fechner Day Meetings

- Engage with the forefront of psychophysical research at our yearly conferences.
- Fechner Day is more than just a meeting—
 - It's an opportunity to network with leading experts and fellow enthusiasts.
 - Share Your Research: Present your findings and receive valuable feedback.
 - Discover Innovations: Stay updated on the latest methods and trends shaping the field.

➤ Professional Development

- Enhance your career through workshops, collaborative projects, and access to exclusive resources.

➤ A Global Community

- Connect with members across continents
- Share your curiosity and commitment to psychophysics.

➤ Be Part of the Future

- Join us in pushing the boundaries of how we perceive the world.
- Whether you're an established professional or an emerging scholar, the International Society for Psychophysics offers a supportive environment to grow, learn, and make a lasting impact.

➤ Become a Member Today!. Apply now: www.ispsychophysics.org/join

➤ Visit our website to learn more about membership benefits

➤ Let's measure the mind together!

International Society for Psychophysics. Chatgpt 1

➤ Join the International Society for Psychophysics!

❑ Are you passionate about understanding how physical stimuli translate into psychological experiences? Become a part of a global community dedicated to advancing the science of psychophysics—the measurement and study of psychological functions.

➤ Who We Are:

❑ Founded in 1984 in the picturesque town of Cassis, France, the International Society for Psychophysics brings together researchers, educators, and practitioners from around the world. Our mission is to deepen the understanding of sensory perception and cognitive processes through rigorous measurement and innovative methodologies.

International Society for Psychophysics.

➤ Input – from Society. No home page. Landing is at News

Inaugurated in Cassis, France in 1984, the International Society for Psychophysics aims to further the study and practise of psychophysics, that is to say, the measurement and study of psychological functions. The society also aims to further the professional development of its members through annual Fechner Day meetings. These are scientific meetings at which the society membership meets to discuss ongoing progress in the development of psychophysical methods and developments or trends within the science itself.

➤ Request to chatgpt

Please rewrite this to attract new members, followed by above text

AI Literature Reviews 1 by ChatGpt Cost

➤ Semantic Scholar

Public Access Free to use

- Especially in computer science, neuroscience, and medicine.
- Recommends related papers, highlights important sections, and provide citation context.

➤ PubMed with AI-powered tools

Free through PubMed

- Database Access: PubMed, which contains biomedical and life sciences literature.
- Elicit, Consensus integrate PubMed for AI-based question, citation analysis, automated summaries.
- Tools for citation analysis, collaboration networks, and trend analysis.

➤ Connected Papers

Public Access Free to use

- Database Access: : many databases to map connected research papers via relevance and citations,
- Provides visual network of related papers, Useful to explore a particular topic deeply.

➤ Scite.ai.

Public Access: Free and paid tiers

- Database Access: Integrates with millions of academic papers
- AI to highlights whether research papers support or contrast with each other. Help with citation analysis and validation

Open Science Foundation NOW

➤ <https://osf.io/> Home. Scroll for content to

As a collaboration tool

OSF helps research teams work on projects privately or make the entire project publicly accessible for broad dissemination. As a workflow system, OSF enables connections to the many products researchers already use, streamlining their process and increasing efficiency.

Structured projects

Manage files, data, code, and protocols in one centralized location and easily build custom organization for your project — no more trawling emails to find files or scrambling to recover lost data.

Controlled access

Manage which parts of a project are public or private, making it easy to collaborate and share with the community or just your team.

Enhanced workflow

Connect your favourite third-party services like Dropbox or Google Drive, automate version control, preregister your research, share preprints.

Dependable repository

OSF's preservation fund is sufficient for 50+ years of read access hosting at present costs.

Radical Statistics 1

➤ About

- ❑ The Radical Statistics Group, usually abbreviated to Radstats, was formed in 1975 as part of the radical science movement associated with the establishment of the British Society for Social Responsibility in Science (BSSRS).
- ❑ The researchers and statisticians who started Radstats shared a common concern about the political implications of their work and an awareness of the actual and potential misuse of statistics. Sadly, neither the BSSRS nor other organizations affiliated to the BSSRS, survived the 18 years of Conservative rule from 1979 to 1997.
- ❑ RadStats is now independent of any other organisation. Members are 'radical' in being committed to helping build a more free, democratic and egalitarian society. Members of Radstats are concerned at the extent to which official statistics reflect governmental rather than social purposes.

➤ Chat

- ❑ The Radical Statistics Group, or Radstats, was founded in 1975 as part of the movement promoting socially responsible science, including the British Society for Social Responsibility in Science (BSSRS). The founders of Radstats were dedicated to examining the role of statistics in society, focusing on how they can be used to support positive social change. Though originally linked to BSSRS, Radstats has evolved into an independent organization committed to fostering a more free, democratic, and egalitarian society.
- ❑ The group's key mission is to ensure that statistics are used ethically and transparently to serve social interests. Members of Radstats are devoted to addressing how official statistics are produced, with an emphasis on aligning them with societal, rather than purely governmental, objectives.

Open Science Foundation 1: chatgpt

➤ **The Open Science Framework (OSF)** is a platform designed to support researchers in managing and sharing their work efficiently. Here is a summary of its key features:

❑ **As a Collaboration Tool**

❑ **Project Management**

OSF allows teams to manage their research projects either privately or publicly, making the sharing and dissemination of work straightforward.

❑ **Workflow Integration:**

It enables seamless integration with many commonly used research tools, increasing efficiency and simplifying workflows.

❑ **Structured Projects**

Centralized Organization: Users can organize all files, data, code, and protocols in one location, reducing the need to search through multiple sources for project information.

❑ **Custom Structure:**

Custom organizational structures can be set up for each project, improving data management and access.

Open Science Foundation chatGPT 0

➤ <https://osf.io/> Home. Scroll for content. Text modified with heading

➤ As a collaboration tool, OSF

Helps research teams work on projects privately or make the entire project publicly accessible for broad dissemination. As a workflow system, OSF enables connections to the many products researchers already use, streamlining their process and increasing efficiency.

➤ Structured projects

Manage file

data, code, and protocols in one centralized location and easily build custom organization for your project — no more trawling emails to find files or scrambling to recover lost data.

➤ Controlled access

Manage which parts of a project are public or private, making it easy to collaborate and share with the community or just your team.

➤ Enhanced workflow

➤ Connect your favourite third-party services

Dropbox or Google Drive,

Automate version control, preregister your research, share preprints.

➤ Dependable repository

➤ OSF's preservation fund

Sufficient for 50+ years of read access hosting at present costs.

Open Science Foundation 1: chatgpt

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-Workflow Integration: It enables seamless integration with many commonly used research tools, increasing efficiency and simplifying workflows.

Structured Projects

Centralized Organization: Users can organize all files, data, code, and protocols in one location, reducing the need to search through multiple sources for project information.

Custom Structure: Custom organizational structures can be set up for each project, improving data management and access.

Controlled Access

Privacy Settings: Users have control over which parts of their projects are visible to the public and which remain private, allowing flexibility in collaboration within the team or broader community.

Enhanced Workflow**

Third-Party Integration: The platform supports connections to external services like Dropbox, Google Drive, and more, helping to automate workflows, manage version control, preregister research, and share preprints.

Dependable Repository**

Long-Term Preservation: OSF's preservation fund ensures that research data and files are hosted with reliable read access for 50+ years at current costs, making it a stable repository for long-term access.

➤ Overall, OSF is designed to streamline research project management, enhance collaboration, and provide dependable data storage.

Open Science Foundation chatGPT 1

- **Join the Open Science Framework (OSF) Community Today!**
- **Are you looking to elevate your research collaboration and streamline your workflow? The Open Science Framework (OSF) is here to transform how you manage, share, and discover research.**
- **Why Choose OSF?**
- **Seamless Collaboration**
 - Private and Public Projects
 - Collaborate effortlessly with your team in a secure, private space,
 - Share your entire project publicly to reach a broader audience and enhance the impact of your work.
- **Centralized Management**
 - Keep all your files, data, code, and protocols in one organized location.
 - Say goodbye to endless email threads and the frustration of lost data.
- **Enhanced Workflow Integration**
 - Connect Your Favourite Tools:
 - Integrate OSF with the research tools you already use
Dropbox, Google Drive, and more.

Open Science Foundation chatGPT 2

➤ Automated Version Control:

- Never lose track of changes. OSF automatically records revisions, Ensure you always have access to previous versions of your work.

➤ Preregistration and Preprints:

- Easily preregister your studies
- Share preprints to promote transparency and accelerate the dissemination of your findings.

➤ Flexible Access Control. Customizable Privacy Settings:

- You decide which parts of your project are public or private.
- Collaborate privately with your team or
- Share your breakthroughs with the global research community.

➤ Community Engagement:

- Engage with other researchers, discover new collaborations
- Contribute to a vibrant, open scientific ecosystem.

➤ Dependable and Long-Term Storage

- A preservation fund ensuring 50+ years of read-access hosting at current costs,
- Your research is safeguarded for the future.

Scholars at Risk NOW

➤ [About](#)

- ❑ Scholars at Risk is an international network of institutions and individuals whose mission it is to protect scholars and promote academic freedom. By arranging temporary academic positions at member universities and colleges, Scholars at Risk offers safety to scholars facing grave threats, so scholars' ideas are not lost and they can keep working until conditions improve and they are able to return to their home countries.
- ❑ Scholars at Risk also provides advisory services for scholars and hosts, campaigns for scholars who are imprisoned or silenced in their home countries, monitoring of attacks on higher education communities worldwide, and leadership in deploying new tools and strategies for promoting academic freedom and improving respect for university values everywhere.

➤ [ChatGPT](#)

- ❑ Scholars at Risk is an international network dedicated to protecting scholars and promoting academic freedom. It helps scholars facing serious threats by arranging temporary academic positions at partner institutions, allowing them to continue their work safely until they can return to their home countries. The organization also provides advisory services, advocates for scholars who are imprisoned or silenced, monitors global attacks on higher education, and develops new strategies to enhance academic freedom and respect for university values.

➤ **Omits individuals and institutions**

Campaign for Science and Engineering

➤ [Home](#)

❑ The Campaign for Science and Engineering (CaSE) is the UK's leading independent advocate for science and engineering. We represent over 115 scientific organisations including businesses, universities, professional bodies, and research charities as well as individual scientists and engineers. Collectively our members employ over 336,000 people in the UK, and our industry and charity members invest around £32.2bn a year globally in R&D.

➤ [Chat 1](#)

❑ The Campaign for Science and Engineering (CaSE) is the UK's leading independent advocate for science and engineering, playing a crucial role in shaping the nation's future. We represent over 115 scientific organizations — spanning businesses, universities, professional bodies, and research charities — alongside individual scientists and engineers. Together, our collective expertise and advocacy influence policies and initiatives that drive progress across all sectors of science and engineering.

➤ **Note chat lost number employed and £ spent**

➤ [Chat Retry](#)

❑ The Campaign for Science and Engineering (CaSE) is the UK's leading independent advocate for science and engineering, representing over 115 scientific organizations, including businesses, universities, professional bodies, and research charities, as well as individual scientists and engineers. Collectively, our member organizations employ over 1 million people in the UK, contributing significantly to the economy and society. In addition, our industry and charity members invest around £32.2 billion a year globally in research and development, driving innovation and technological progress across various sectors.

Radical Statistics 2

➤ About Concerns

- ❑ The mystifying use of technical language to disguise social problems as technical ones
- ❑ The lack of control by the community over the aims of statistical investigations, the way these are conducted and the use of the information produced
- ❑ The power structures within which statistical and research workers are employed and which control the work and how it is used
- ❑ The fragmentation of social problems into specialist fields, obscuring connectedness

➤ Chat Our core areas of focus include:

- ❑ Ensuring that statistical language is clear and transparent, so social issues are not disguised as mere technical challenges.
- ❑ Empowering communities to have greater input and oversight over the aims, methodologies, and uses of statistical investigations, ensuring that data serves the interests of society as a whole.
- ❑ Addressing the influence of power structures in the employment of statistical and research professionals, advocating for work that is free from undue control and can be used for the public good.
- ❑ Promoting a holistic approach to social issues by preventing their separation into overly specialized fields, which can obscure their interconnectedness and hinder comprehensive solutions.

➤ **Chat is worse. Longer more buzz word – e.g. holistic, empowering**

AI Literature Reviews 2 by chatGPT Cost

➤ [Iris.ai](#)

Public Access: Paid service, but some features

offer free access

- Database Access: Open Access publications, PubMed, and other academic databases.
- AI-driven research tools for literature review, research summaries, and data extraction.

➤ [ResearchRabbit](#)

Public Access: Free to use

- Database Access: various academic databases for paper discovery and analysis.
- AI Features helps researchers track new research and build networks of related work.

➤ [Consensus](#)

Free access to core feature

- Database Access: Aggregates research from databases like PubMed and Google Scholar.
- AI answers to specific research questions based on aggregated results from academic papers.

➤ [Dimensions](#) detailed data)

Limited free access (premium access for

- Database Access: Academic articles, clinical trials, patents, and datasets.

AI for Literature Reviews chatGPT Score

Tool	Score	Source			
Semantic Scholar	4.8/5	G2	Product Hunt		
Scite.ai	4.7/5	G2		ResearchGate	
Iris.ai	4.5/5			ResearchGate	Capterra
Connectedpapers	4.5/5		Product Hunt		Capterra
Consensus	4.4/5	G2	Product Hunt		

No mention

World of Science, pubmed, Scopus, google scholar

Summary

- **Quantification has always been a key tool in advancing knowledge of psychology**
 - ❑ Started in 19C detection, RT, sensation
 - ❑ 20C produces scales intelligence, mental illness, evaluation and statistical techniques
- **Open Science**
 - ❑ Not conceptually new
 - ❑ 21C codifies: particularly open methods, data and code
- **Artificial Intelligence**
 - ❑ New tools: powerful and potentially dangerous
 - ❑ Rapidly developing
 - ❑ Will advance psychophysics

Thanks

➤ Thanks to all for listening

- ❑ Collaboration welcome from AI users & explorers

➤ Special thanks to Narayanan

- ❑ For organising great conference
- ❑ For giving me this opportunity